

INVESTMENT IS THE POWER THAT DEVELOPS THE TOURISM OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract: Investments in various forms have become an integral part of every country in the world. In this article we will consider the basics of investment activity: the nature and types of investments, investment risks and investment strategies.

Key words: investment, investment, investor, economic growth.

1. Introduction

It is known from the history of mankind that for the development of any sphere (production, service) it is necessary first of all to have a capital, that is, progress without investment can not be achieved. The sphere of service, production, as well as modernization of the country, technical and technological new investments can not be imagined without foreign investment in particular. It is worth noting that tourism has all the infrastructure associated with it (transport, placement, feeding, it has a direct impact on the development of entertainment and other additional services), resulting in its transformation into a highly profitable sector of the country's economy. In addition, the development of Tourism of the country will be the main impetus for the expansion of cooperation between the countries of the world, attracting foreign direct investment into the sphere and popularizing the country's tourist potential. Tourism (French: tour-Travel, Travel), Tourism-Travel (Travel) ; one of the types of active recreation. Tourism means the departure (travel) of an individual from a permanent place of residence for a period

of 1 year without the participation of a paid activity in a place (country) for health, educational, professional, practical or other purposes. The history of Tourism dates back to the beginning of the XIX century. Initially, organized tourism was established from England to France (1815). Thomas Kuk, an English psychic who was considered the founder of mass tourism, founded the 1st railway tourism in 1843. After that, he will establish his own private tourist enterprise and in 1866 year will send the first tourist groups to the United States. Starting his journey at the age of 21, the arab traveler Ibn Butauta in the East came out of almost all the Eastern and North African countries, the kezib in the Poda. In the Great Commander and statesman, sahibkiran Amir Temur, who made a great contribution to the world civilization, the first trips of tourists to the powerful saltanat Movarounnahr, which restored Amir Temur, were active during the period of Amir Temur and Temurids. Amir Temur was in constant contact with the French King Carl VI and the English King Henry IV. His ambassador came to Paris in 1403-th year. In the book "The Life and activity of the Great Timur" of Spanish Claudico, the social life in Movarounnahr and the aspiration of tourists to the Timur state were reflected. At present, Tourism has received a mass influx in many countries of the world. At the present stage of the development of mankind at a high pace of socio-economic development, the increase in the level of population stagnation and prosperity, the increase in the level of urbanization (urbanization), the emergence of free time, led to a radical change in the characteristics of social values and personal residence. These, in turn, the adaptation of the lifestyle of the population to these changes, it serves as an important basis for a significant increase in demand and needs for recreation and tourism. Accordingly, travel, active rest in the bosom of nature has become a component of the life of modern

people, as well as an important form of strengthening health and effective use of free time. At the same time, if earlier in tourism there was a dominant goal of obtaining just pleasure, without thinking about anything, then at the moment such goals have radically changed: the place of sluggishness was occupied by the pursuit of active leisure; the place of active recreation of one person was occupied by the desire to rest as many or at least two people. Other goals from the tourism trip have also changed: secluded individuality in the past, and now ruined leisure; clear planning in the past, and now free satisfaction of the desired need; in the past, the full consumption of the blessings of civilization (civilization), and now the presence in the bosom of nature came to the fore. Tourism is an important source of intensive development of business activities and the economy of the regions, creating many new jobs, additional incomes, rich and diverse cultural-historical, natural objects (see below), and environmental protection), as well as effective directions of use through monitoring on the basis of the provision of natural protection and environmental safety. Any investment in tourism is an investment in the future. About this, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoyev points out: -world experience shows that which state has pursued an active investment policy has achieved a stable growth of its economy. For this reason, investment is an economic driver, in Uzbek terms, the heart of the economy, if we say so, will not be an exaggeration. Attracting investments in the tourism industry is an investment, the creation of new tourist facilities with the help of capital, the modernization or reconstruction of existing ones and their use.

Investment - (from the German word "investment", Latin "Investio"), which is mainly interpreted as the cost of long-term investments in production, that is, the

sum of costs. Investment is all kinds of wealth invested by the state, legal entities and individuals (investors) for a certain period of time in various sectors of the economy in order to effectively meet the unlimited need, with the aim of obtaining profit (income) or achieving social effect. Investments are considered an integral part of the modern economy, these are funds used for the development and expansion of production, services, as well as capital investments. Investment is the putting of funds for the purpose of obtaining profit in the future. Investment means linking or keeping capital for a certain period of time. The main purpose of this is to preserve the value of capital or to grow the value of capital if it is not. The economic content of the investment reflects the material, intangible assets and rights to them, which are mobilized into various activities. As an investment, money, Securities (shares, bonds, certificates, bills), wealth such as land, buildings, structures, scientific discoveries, inventions, etc., which are real property, are used. Those who invest in investment projects-investors can be state, company, Enterprise, foreign citizens, residents and entrepreneurs. When it comes to attracting investments in tourism, it is understood to place the capital of investors in the tourist business for the purpose of making a profit.

Considering the future development of the country's tourism and its economy, in particular, its dependence on investment, one of the important issues today is the wider attraction of investment in tourism, in particular foreign investment. The presence of a favorable investment climate in the country creates great opportunities for local and foreign investors to freely invest their funds in tourism. This in turn, it serves the development of the country's tourism. At present, the rapid development of tourism requires the attraction of large-scale investments. Because if investments remain the tourism of the country, it is the

power that drives the economy of the countries of the world and ensures its development. As an example of this, it is planned to direct investments in the Russian country in the amount of 174,65 billion rubles for the implementation of the state program of the city of Moscow "development of the leisure and tourism industry in 2012-2018 years" for the city of Moscow. - 159,2 billion rubles, 7492,883 million rubles for the Krasnodar Territory, 4011,837 million rubles for the Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol, 1086,4 million rubles for the Republic of Tatarstan, 1578,386 million rubles for Buryatia, 7216,469 million rubles for Chuvashia, 735,771 million rubles for the Kamchatka territory are allocated, investments in the country of Uzbekistan in 2016, 46.4 billion soums. according to the forecast figures for 2018 to 2021, 75.8 billion manat was recorded in the first quarter of 2017. it can be said that the sum will increase. The sphere of tourism is one of the most dynamically developing spheres of the world economy. Its extensive development is becoming a major source of revenue for many countries. Therefore, many countries of the world are implementing all measures to further develop this sphere, to create the appropriate infrastructure at the level of world standards and to increase the flow of tourists. This is reflected in the following figures; that is, in terms of the reception of foreign guests, it accounts for France (83,7 million), the United States (74,8 million), Spain (65,0 million), China (55,6 million) and Italy (48,6 million). These countries occupied a strong five-point position, while Germany, Great Britain, Russia and Mexico occupied a strong ten-point position.

In developing tourism business it is necessary to take into account the following factors: :

* measures to determine the parameters and prospects of development for the implementation of capacity, financing, management-organizational measures and deadlines aimed at solving urgent problems and strategic tasks;

• the volume of domestic, foreign tourism flows, the availability of tourism facilities and the capacity to receive them the highest, the possibilities of tourism infrastructure facilities;

* programming activities to increase investment activity;

* Strategic forecast of tourism development: conception, strategy, medium term forecast ,eksex program.

The following important factors are taken into account when assessing the country's investment potential:

– factors of production (general results of economic activity in the country);

– consumer factor (total purchasing power of the population of the country);

– infrastructural factor (itisodi-geographic situation of the country and its infrastructural provision);

– intellectual factor (level of education of the population);

In conclusion, I would like to say that since tourism is one of the most profitable spheres, many countries of the world also pay special attention to the development of this sphere. As a result of the development of the tourism sector, the position of the country in the world community is strengthened, international economic relations are improved, new opportunities, conditions and reliable cooperation for local and foreign investors are opened, entrepreneurial activity develops and the country's macroeconomic indicators are stabilized, the employment of the population increases and the income of the population increases, and the sphere of services improves. To do this, of course, it is necessary

not only to attract local and foreign investments, but also to use them wisely and efficiently. For all local and foreign entrepreneurs (investors) wishing to operate in the tourism sector in the country, it is necessary to create and maintain a healthy competitive environment between them, creating all opportunities, conditions and benefits. Because where there is competition, there will be a rise, development.

Reference

1. Frederic S. Mishkin & Stanley G. Eakins. 2012. Financial Markets and Institution\Eighth Edition.
2. Murodovna, R. G. (2021). Analytical procedure in an audit of fixed assets. International Journal of Financial Management and Economics International Journal of Financial Management and Economics, 4(1), 41-45P.
3. Rahimova G. (2021). Accounting of the results of continuous revaluation of property, plant and equipment in accordance with international standards. Society and innovations, (Общество и инновации) (Жамият ва ва инновациялар) 3(2021) / ISSN 2181-1415.
4. Rakhimova G. (2021). The main instrument of calculation is the theoretical justification of the stratification of flour into the current state and people's standards./ International multidisciplinary scientific conferences on the DIALOGUE BETWEEN SCIENCE & ARTS, RELIGION/ 65-67 P.
5. <https://www.invesco.com/us-rest/contentdetail?contentId>.
6. Murynov A.A. Taxation of sub-federal securities and local government financial flows. <https://cyberleninka.ru>.
7. Novikov A. 1997. Instruments of the municipal securities market abroad // Securities market. № 4. p. 25-30.